

Osmium(VIII)-catalysed Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol by Hexacyano-ferrate(III) in Alkaline Medium

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The osmium(VIII) catalysis in a number of organic and inorganic reactions in alkaline medium has been studied¹. In these studies a complex formation between catalyst and substrate is observed. Hexacyanoferrate(III) is an efficient oxidising agent in alkaline medium. The kinetic and mechanistic studies involving this oxidant have been reviewed². In the present communication, we describe the title reaction.

Results and Discussion

The reaction orders were determined from log-log plots of initial rate vs concentration. The order in allyl alcohol was fractional (~0.3) in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-3} to 4.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ (Table 1). Plots of log [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] vs time were linear upto 70% of reaction and above this, deviation from linearity were observed. The first order rate constants were constant over the Fe(CN)₆³⁻ concentration range of 8.0×10^{-5} to 6.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. Hence the order in oxidant is unity. The order in [OH⁻] is less than unity (~0.3).

The effect of the concentration of catalyst Os^{VIII} on rates of reaction, keeping all other concentrations constant, is shown in Table 1. The rate increased with the increase in concentration of the catalyst. The order in Os^{VIII} is approximately unity.

The effect of initially added Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ was studied in the concentration range of 1.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ keeping the ionic strength and concentrations of reactants constant. The rate retarded with increase of [Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻] (Table 2) and the order with respect to this product was -0.40. The effect of acrolein on the reaction could not be studied as it was unstable because of its tendency to polymerise readily; use of stabilising agents was not thought desirable.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PRODUCT

[AA] = 1.0×10^{-2} , [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] = 4.0×10^{-4} , [OH ⁻] = 4.0×10^{-2} , [Os ^{VIII}] = 5.0×10^{-5} , I = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³									
[Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻] × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³	0	1.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	9.0	10.0	
Rate × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	1.73	1.69	1.66	1.63	1.57	1.44	1.38	1.24	

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [Os^{VIII}], [AA], [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] AND [OH⁻] ON THE Os^{VIII} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL BY HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)

I = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³					
10 ² [AA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ [Os ^{VIII}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ Initial rate mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
				Exptl.	Calcd.
0.1	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	0.7
0.2	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.1	1.0
0.4	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.4	1.4
0.6	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.5	1.6
1.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.7	1.7
2.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.8	2.0
3.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.9	2.2
1.0	0.8	5.0	4.0	0.5	0.4
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	0.8	0.9
1.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	1.5	1.4
1.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.7	1.7
1.0	6.0	5.0	4.0	2.2	2.6
1.0	4.0	0.7	4.0	0.19	0.24
1.0	4.0	1.0	4.0	0.28	0.36
1.0	4.0	2.5	4.0	0.83	0.94
1.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.7	1.7
1.0	4.0	10	4.0	3.2	3.6
1.0	4.0	20	4.0	5.8	6.5
1.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	0.95	0.78
1.0	4.0	5.0	2.0	1.1	1.2
1.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.8	1.8
1.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	1.9	2.2
1.0	4.0	5.0	8.0	2.1	2.4

Increase in ionic strength in the range 0.04 and 0.3 mol dm⁻³ increased the rate of reaction. The plot of log rate vs I^{1/2} was linear (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH

[AA] = 1.0×10^{-2} , [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] = 4.0×10^{-4} , [OH ⁻] = 4.0×10^{-2} , [Os ^{VIII}] = 5.0×10^{-5} , mol dm ⁻³					
I mol dm ⁻³	0.04	0.08	0.10	0.15	0.30
Rate × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	1.2	1.5	1.7	2.0	2.8

When the reaction mixture containing acrylamide was kept over 24 h and diluted with methanol, no precipitate appeared showing the absence of intervention of free radical.

The reaction kinetics were also studied at 25, 30, 35 and 40° [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 4×10^{-4} ; [AA] = 0.01; [OH⁻] = 0.02; I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ resulting in rate constant values of 3.61×10^{-3} , 4.2×10^{-3} , 4.8×10^{-3} and 5.6×10^{-3} s⁻¹ respectively. Activation parameters E_a (22.30 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹) and ΔS^\ddagger (-221.76 ± 4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹) were calculated from these data.

Rate law : The rate law (1) for the reaction follows from the experimental results,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]_T[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{AA}]^{0.3}[\text{OH}^-]^3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]^{-0.4} \quad (1)$$

The results of the study on the Os^{VIII} -catalysed reaction are in agreement with the formation of a complex between the catalyst and substrate followed by its oxidation by $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, which is the rate-determining step. Attempts to obtain spectral evidence for the complex failed since there was no appreciable change in the electronic spectra of the substrate and catalyst in presence of each other. However, the interaction may be feeble and such complex formation between the catalyst and substrate has also been observed in other studies³. The evidence for complex formation is restricted to kinetic data. All the experimental results are in agreement with Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 leads to rate law (2)

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{OH}^-][\text{AA}]\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}}{(1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-])(1 + K_2[\text{AA}])} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), the denominator must also contain the factor $(1 + K_3)/[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ which is left out since it approximates to unity. It may be noted that the reaction between the complex (C) and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ is rate-determining and the formation of Os^{VIII} in the intermediate steps has also been observed by earlier workers⁴. The one equivalent steps written in Scheme 1 are in agreement with the fact that single electron transfers are more probable than others. The retardation of rate by ferrocyanide has been attributed to a secondary salt effect as noticed also by earlier workers⁵.

The mechanism (Scheme 1) and rate law (2) was verified by a linear plot of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[\text{AA}]$. From the slope, intercept and K_1 (which is taken as $22 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ from the earlier work¹), the values of K_2 ($364 \pm 20 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and k_1 ($2.45 \times 10^3 \pm 0 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) were obtained. These values were further used to calculate rates for several experimental situations. Rates calculated in this way are compared with the experimentally measured rates in Table 1 and

they show good agreement. The increase in rate with ionic strength is as expected qualitatively from the mechanism (Scheme 1) where ions of like charge interact in rate-determining steps. The observed large negative value of entropy of activation is indicative of the formation of activated complex in the reaction.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The stock solutions of hexacyanoferrate(III) were prepared by dissolving a known quantity of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (AnalaR) and standardised iodometrically⁶. Allyl alcohol (Koch light) was purified⁷ and its solution was standardised by addition of excess chloramine-T followed by iodometric titration⁸. The Os^{VIII} solution was made by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson Matthey) in 0.5 M NaOH. The concentration was ascertained⁹ by standardising with addition of excess ferrocyanide and the excess estimated with standard Ce^{IV} solution. The hexacyanoferrate(II) solution was prepared from $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (B.D.H.). The ionic strength was kept constant with sodium perchlorate.

The reaction was initiated by mixing requisite quantities of allyl alcohol, hexacyanoferrate(III), Os^{VIII} in alkali and sodium perchlorate. The reaction mixture was transferred to a quartz cell (1 cm) and then placed in the thermostated cell compartment of a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer and the absorbance of hexacyanoferrate(III) at 420 nm was followed. The obedience to Beers law of the absorption of hexacyanoferrate(III) at 420 nm in the range of 8×10^{-5} to $6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ was tested earlier ($\epsilon = 1060 \pm 1.5\%$). Kinetic runs were studied under pseudo-first order condition with alcohol concentration in excess over that of oxidant at $27 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Initial rates were calculated by plane mirror method¹⁰ and were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry: Different sets of reactant concentrations in $4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH at constant ionic strength of 0.10 M , were kept for over 24 h at 27° and then analysed for hexacyanoferrate(II) by measuring absorbance at 420 nm; under the condition $[\text{AA}] > [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$, the unreacted allyl alcohol was estimated by the addition of excess chloramine-T and unreacted chloramine-T was estimated iodometrically. The product hexacyanoferrate(II) was found by oxidising it to hexacyanoferrate(III) and measuring the absorbance of the latter at 420 nm. Another product acrolein, was identified¹¹ by spot test. The tests for acrylic acid were negative. The stoichiometry was understood as two moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) required to oxidise one mole of allyl alcohol,

$$2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCH}_2\text{OH} \xrightarrow{\text{Os}^{8+}} 2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCHO} + 2\text{H}^+$$

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